

ELEPHANT ENDOTHELIOTROPIC HERPES VIRUS HEMORRHAGIC DISEASE: AN EMERGING THREAT

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ABSTRACT

Elephant endotheliotropic herpesvirus haemorrhagic disease (EEHV HD) is the major cause of death in young Asian and African elephants with the mortality rate of about 85%. It is a moderately understood emerging disease which causes highly fatal acute hemorrhagic infection caused by distinct strains of two different variants of herpes virus which has been a constant threat to the conservation and management of elephants worldwide. EEHVs are the endemic viruses in elephants having co-evolved with elephants with a million of years. Since EEHV is a non-cultivable virus, there is a scarcity of specific diagnosis, therapeutics and vaccines. The review explores and aims in summarizing the current status and idea of EEHV, its etiology, emergence, diagnosis, clinical presentation, prevention of the deadly disease.

Keywords: Elephant, endotheliotropic, herpesvirus, mortality, emergence

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